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Title

Summary of intermittent preventive treatment in school children (IPTsc) contextual factors

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Summary of IPTsc contextual factors

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Executive Summary

Background

Despite substantial advances in malaria control, the last few years have seen a rise in malaria cases, prompting a reassessment of optimal control measures. School-age children have a high prevalence of infection and are least likely to use insecticide treated nets (ITNs). Nevertheless, they are not typically the target of malaria chemoprevention interventions. A recent review demonstrated a beneficial impact amongst school-aged children receiving chemoprevention on both *Plasmodium falciparum* infections and anemia. This document summarizes the main findings from published studies with data on contextual factors related to IPTsc implementation, including acceptability, feasibility, equity, and costs/cost-effectiveness.

Methods

We searched Medline through Jan 31, 2022 without time or language restrictions. Additionally, we reviewed articles included in Cohee et al. as well as those identified in the update to the quantitative analysis for relevant contextual information. Two reviewers screened articles to identify those which discussed the administration of a full course of antimalarial administration to school aged children, irrespective of symptoms, and without testing for malaria and extracted information on a pre-piloted electronic data extraction form. Data on acceptability, feasibility, health equity, and cost were summarized in a text summary.

Results

Out of 351 unique articles we identified 16 studies with relevant information. Very little data was identified on values and preferences, with only a note that there may be a preference to treat sicker appearing children. In general, acceptability was high among both parents and teachers, though there were reports in some countries of parents harboring suspicion around the drug administration programs. Clear communication needs to go out to the community to prevent rumors that impact coverage. Adverse event rates depended upon the specific drugs used, but severe adverse events were exceedingly rare, and in general, studies reported that they did not impact uptake, though some community interviews suggested that they did. This is an issue which deserves attention in implementing a new program. From a health equity standpoint, studies on school-based ITN distribution suggest that this is largely an equitable strategy, though slightly favors less poor households. IPTsc is generally cost effective, and cost-effectiveness can be further improved by combining

antimalarial drug distribution with other on-going programs; cost is highly dependent on the choice of drug and frequency of administration. There is some evidence that IPTsc selects for resistant parasites, but it is less clear to what extent this actually drives overall resistance at community level.

Conclusions

Overall, IPTsc appears to be a generally acceptable and feasible strategy, but there remain operational considerations around the best means to deploy IPTsc, optimal drugs and frequency of administration, and how to ensure high coverage is maintained. Considerations should also be given as to which areas should be targeted, with consideration given to ensure equitable access, and a plan to monitor for development of resistance should be included in any implementation plan.

Background

Despite substantial advances in malaria control at the end of the 20th and early 21st century, with a reduction in malaria deaths from 896,000 in 2000 to 558,000 in 2019, the last few years have seen a rise in malaria cases, necessitating reconsideration of deployment of optimal packages of interventions to prevent and treat malaria. Recent studies have demonstrated that school-age children (6-to-15 year olds) often have a higher prevalence of infection than younger children and adults.¹⁻⁴ Additionally, due to the high prevalence of infection as well as gametocytes (in community surveys in Malawi, 46% of all gametocyte-containing infections were in school-age children, who comprised only 35% of the population), school-aged children may be an important human infectious reservoir for malaria.⁴⁻⁸ Furthermore, school-age children are the least likely to use bed nets compared to other ages increasing the odds of being bitten by mosquitos.^{9,10} Nevertheless, they are not typically the target of most malaria prevention interventions such as intermittent preventive treatment in infants and seasonal malaria chemoprevention (SMC) which generally target children 3-59 months. There is, however, interest in reaching school-aged children to improve child health and to reduce community-level malaria. For example, expansion of SMC in Senegal to include children aged 5-10 years was associated with a 20% decrease in clinical malaria among older community members who did not receive the intervention.¹¹ Improving access to preventive measures among school-aged children will benefit the children themselves, and may have additional community level benefit in reducing transmission.¹² One option that has been deployed is intermittent preventive treatment delivered to school-aged children, or IPTsc. Trials conducted to date have varied in the number of rounds and drugs used, leading to substantial heterogeneity in the observed effects. However, the recent review from Cohee et al. demonstrated a beneficial impact amongst children receiving the intervention on both *Plasmodium falciparum* infections and anemia.¹³ Some trials have also demonstrated improvements in attention and certain cognitive functions.¹⁴ This document summarizes the main findings from published studies with data on contextual factors related to IPTsc implementation, including acceptability, feasibility, equity, and costs/cost-effectiveness.

Methods

We searched medline using the following search terms (**intermittent prevent* treat***) **AND malaria AND child* AND (value OR knowledg* OR Accept* OR Feasib* OR equit* OR cost OR resource)** through Jan 31, 2022 without time or language restrictions. In addition, we reviewed articles identified in the update to the quantitative analysis (see Appendix) from Dec 15, 2018 (the final date included by Cohee et al.) to 12/23/2021, as well as reviewed all articles included in Cohee et al. for relevant contextual information. In addition, reference lists of included articles were screened for possible studies missed by the search. Two reviewers independently screened titles and abstracts identified from literature searches. The same two reviewers evaluated any potentially relevant articles identified by at least one reviewer for full-text eligibility based on pre-determined inclusion criteria: studies discussed the administration of a full course of antimalarial administration to school aged children, irrespective of symptoms, and without testing for malaria. Disagreements were resolved by consensus. Two reviewers independently extracted information from studies on a pre-piloted electronic data extraction form. Any

discrepancies in information were resolved by consensus or by consultation with a third reviewer. Data was then summarized in a text summary.

Information on the following was extracted:

- **Values and preferences:** Information on the relative importance assigned to health outcomes by those affected by them; how such importance varies within and across populations; and whether this importance or variability is surrounded by uncertainty.
- **Acceptability:** The extent to which those benefiting from an intervention as well as other relevant stakeholder groups consider the intervention to be appropriate, based on anticipated or experienced cognitive and emotional responses to the intervention
- **Feasibility and health system considerations:** Barriers to implementation (i.e. resources available, programmatic considerations, existing and necessary infrastructure), interaction with existing health system, need for and use of the existing health workforce (including training)
- **Financial and economic considerations:** The cost, overall economic impact, cost-benefit, and/or cost-effectiveness
- **Health equity, equality and non-discrimination:** The extent to which the intervention benefits all populations, does not discriminate against anyone on the basis of sex, age, ethnicity, culture, language, sexual orientation or gender identity, disability status, education, SES status, residence or any other characteristic. This could include whether the benefits and harms are equally distributed and whether the intervention is equally affordable and accessible to all.

Results

The searches combined yielded a total of 461 articles, with 110 duplicates, for a total of 351 unique articles. Of these, 170 studies were excluded based on title/ abstract review. The full text of 181 articles were reviewed; 165 were excluded (133 were the wrong intervention, 12 wrong patient population, 3 were ongoing studies, 1 was a duplicate study population, 12 articles had the wrong outcomes, and 4 had no primary data). A total of 16 studies were included.

Values and preferences

There was only one article which addressed the values and preferences of communities and families with respect to malaria and IPTsc. In situations where one member of the household is ill, but a different member receives presumptive therapy, the drug may be used on the sick person rather than on the person who was actually given the medication, as reported by Okello et al: "In one FGD, a CHW working for the trial reported that a parent had used her child's medication, given to him after testing in school, to treat another sibling who was perceived to be sicker."¹⁵

Acceptability

Overall, few studies directly assessed the acceptability of a school-based approach to deliver malaria chemoprevention, but this was generally viewed as an acceptable option. One study in Uganda noted that there was substantial suspicion surrounding the program, which improved following community sensitization. This is an important consideration for programs deciding to implement such a program, and highlights the critical importance of providing sufficient sensitization in advance of implementation.

Clarke et al. noted that the taste of the medicine could influence acceptability and adherence to the complete regimen, as children receiving IPT with SP-amodiaquine (which has a bitter taste) were less likely to receive all doses than children receiving placebo, however, studies undertaken after completion of the trial showed the IPT strategy to be well accepted by teachers, parents, and schoolchildren.¹⁴ Nankabirwa et al. similarly noted that children receiving active drug (SPAQ or DP) were more likely to rate the taste of the tablets as 'poor' or 'fair' (versus 'good' or 'excellent') as compared to children receiving placebo. Despite this, 93% of children reported that they would be willing or very willing to take the tablets each school term, regardless of treatment group.¹⁶

In Côte d'Ivoire, compliance to two rounds of IPT for malaria (with SP) and anthelmintics delivered 3 months apart as part of a placebo controlled, randomized clinical trial was high, at 93.7%, suggesting that the treatment was acceptable. Though this may be higher because participants consented individually, only one person approached for enrollment refused to participate, and 554/591 enrolled school children completed the study.¹⁷

In a study conducted in Uganda, Staedke et al found that some community members were initially suspicious of the IPT intervention.¹² A substantial investment was made in terms of community engagement, which improved uptake of the intervention. In a pilot study in Malawi, it was noted that adding malaria treatment to an existing school-based mass drug administration programme was associated with high coverage among school children (87%), suggesting that there might be better acceptability of combining the intervention with already existing health programs.¹⁸

With respect to a screening strategy deployed in a school based intermittent screen and treat (IST) program, Okello et al. reported "While IST was clearly perceived to contribute to a reduction in clinical disease, few participants appear to have been aware that the principal aim of IST is the reduction of asymptomatic parasitaemia, rather than the treatment of clinical disease. Although this lack of awareness did not appear to impact on the acceptability of the intermittent screening component of the intervention, the findings do suggest that it may affect willingness to adhere to the full treatment regime"¹⁵ This has relevance for an IPTsc programme as well, particularly if consideration is given to providing a student with one dose under directly observed therapy and distributing the remaining doses to be taken at home.

Audibert et al. conducted a qualitative study to assess perceptions of chemoprevention.¹⁹ While this focused largely on seasonal malaria chemoprevention (SMC) and IPT in infants, some of the perceptions are relevant to IPTsc. In general, people found the drug to be very effective, and from a household perspective, noted that the preventive chemotherapy saved them money as it reduced the need for treatment.¹⁹ Parents recommended that SMC be expanded to include older children and even adults,

and provide coverage for longer than four months.¹⁹ Staff noted that there were issues with acceptance from parents, particularly in cases where there were side effects from the drugs, parents would refuse the 2nd and 3rd days of treatment, and noted that acceptance was lower with subsequent rounds.¹⁹ In order to improve uptake of SMC, staff suggested ensuring parents are well educated about the program; this also has relevance to IPTsc.¹⁹

With respect to adverse events and severe adverse events, studies reported a range of events, which may be expected given that different drug combinations were used in each study. In general, only mild, self-limited adverse events were reported and they were not associated with discontinuation of treatment regimens or programs. Nonetheless, the potential side effects of the drugs to be used must be carefully considered, particularly for distribution to healthy school children.

Adverse events

Among Ugandan students who received IPT-DP, a total of 17 severe adverse reactions were noted, including 2 deaths (both considered unrelated to DP). Only two of these were considered possibly related to drug administration (an allergic skin reaction and hypoglycemia resulting in loss of consciousness).¹² Among 6758 students (3535 in the IPT arm (SPAQ) and 3223 in the placebo) Clarke et al. reported 23 serious adverse events, 19 in the IPT arm (three judged to be drug related) and four in the placebo arm.¹⁴ In addition, seven deaths were reported, 2 in the IPT arm and 5 in the placebo arm.¹⁴ Nankabirwa et al. assessed the efficacy of a single course of SP, SPAQ, or DP among 780 asymptomatic school children, and noted a very high proportion (61%) of children reporting an adverse event, though the vast majority (92%) were mild, with no severe adverse events.¹⁶ Among 296 Malian students randomized to receive two rounds of either SPAS, ASAQ, or vitamin C, side effects were generally mild. Headache was reported most commonly for both rounds of treatment, with rates between 4-14% of students per arm per round; abdominal pain was the second most common complaint occurring in 0-7% of students per arm per round. Other reported events (vomiting, diarrhea, cough, wheeze) occurred in <5% of students. No students elected to quit the study because of adverse events.^{20,21} Another study in Mali including 941 students in a single round of IPTp with SPAS versus 940 in the control arm found few adverse events reported by teachers, mainly stomach ache and vomiting immediately after treatment, with most symptoms being mild and self-limiting.²² No severe adverse effects related to the administration of SPAS were reported.²² In DRC, among 404 children who received IPT with either SP or SP+ piperazine, no deaths or SAEs were reported. There was no difference in the proportion of children with adverse events when comparing SP to control, however, there were more children with dizziness in the SP+ piperazine arm compared to control.

Health equity, equality and non-discrimination

There is very limited data on how a school-based platform for delivery of malaria chemoprevention to children would affect equity and health equality. Findings from Staedke et al suggest that there is the potential for school-based distribution strategies to fail to provide equitable access for young women of reproductive age.¹² Given that many drugs would not be recommended for use in women in first

trimester of pregnancy, it may be operationally easier to exclude all girls of reproductive age, as this avoids addressing the issue of pregnancy detection, however, this strategy also denies these girls the possible benefits of IPT. Therefore, programs need to carefully consider how to address the issue of possible early pregnancy such that they do not exclude all girls of reproductive age. In addition to creating inequitable distribution, this can lead to increased suspicion and poorer uptake of the intervention.

An additional equity consideration raised by the authors of the Uganda study is that children residing in urban areas may already be at lower risk of malaria than their rural counterparts, and thus the added benefit of IPT in such settings may be lower.²³ They highlight the need to further explore the role of providing IPT for schoolchildren in urban settings.

Finally, there is a need to carefully consider how school enrollment affects equity. First, the children in lowest socioeconomic strata are likely to be at highest risk for malaria, as well as least likely to be enrolled in school/ most likely to dropout, and school absenteeism may also be more likely in children of lower socioeconomic status as well as with illnesses. Mantangila et al. reported "The expected number of schoolchildren was 650 per school at the beginning of the year, with an absenteeism rate of 40% and a school drop-out rate of 20% reported by school directors."²⁴ Staedke et al. noted that in Uganda, while 82% of primary-school-aged children were reported to attend school, there was substantial absenteeism, particularly in rural areas.¹² This highlights the extent to which a school-based platform may miss targeted children. Thus, programs may want to consider how to provide access for school-aged children who are not enrolled or not present in school on the days when drug distribution occurs.

Given the limited information available on IPTsc distribution, data on school-based ITN distribution was also examined. de Beyl et al. reported on the results of several continuous ITN distribution channels, noting that while they were largely equitable, they were slightly more likely to be accessed by households from wealthier quintiles.²⁵ Additionally, school registration data from Tanzania demonstrates that school drop-out rates increase as students progress to higher grades, thus this mechanism is more effective at targeting primary school aged children, though these are also the children with the highest burden of malaria.

Distribution of antimalarials in schools in areas of higher endemicity/ focal hotspots could have very positive effects on overall health equity.

Feasibility and health system considerations

Schools provide a potential platform for delivery of various health interventions; in some countries they already provide nutrition services and are sites of targeted ITN distribution and deworming programs. Teachers may be seen as trusted messengers, and schools often serve as focal points for societal and behaviour change communication.²³ Thus, utilizing schools to provide IPT is an attractive option, however, there are feasibility considerations to ensure that coverage is high and that appropriate communications reach the community to ensure awareness, understanding, and buy-in of the program.

One important consideration is choice of drug regimen. Commenting on a study in Kenya utilizing artemether-lumefantrine, Okello et al. noted that this was a very complex regimen, as it required six doses to be administered, each with food, which could present a major challenge for a school-based distribution program.¹⁵ They further suggested that using a simpler antimalarial regimen would enhance compliance, ideally single dose regimens which allow directly observed therapy.^{13,15} Many programs looking at IPT have utilized SP, both given its well documented safety and tolerability, low cost, and ease of administration as a single dose.²⁶⁻²⁸ In West Africa, the efficacy of SP remains reasonable, particularly if used in combination with another efficacious drug,^{29,30} however, resistance to SP may preclude the use of SP in areas southern and eastern Africa.¹³ Matangila et al. assessed the use of SP alone or in combination with piperazine at baseline, month 4, and month 7 among school children in DRC.²⁴ IPTsc with SP + piperazine was more efficacious than SP alone, despite the relatively low prevalence of *pfdhpsA540E* (<10%), and the authors note that this quarterly regimen would be more feasible to implement than a monthly regimen.²⁴ As long-acting drugs require fewer administrations to cover the same time period as shorter acting drugs, they are generally preferred from a feasibility standpoint, however, these drugs also provide the longest period during which parasite resistance can develop.¹³ Thus, the advantages of providing long duration of prophylaxis must be balanced against efficacy, safety, tolerability, and the potential of drugs to select for resistance.¹³

In Uganda, Staedke et al. had relatively low uptake of a school-based intervention, with only 43% of registered students receiving at least one dose, and coverage from surveys showing even lower coverage with 12-37% of surveyed children receiving of any dose.¹² Poor uptake in this study was attributed to a number of factors, including community (mis)perceptions about IPT and the requirement for parental informed consent to be obtained for each student.¹² A trial by Clarke et al. in western Kenya assessing the effect of 3 rounds of SP-amodiaquine administered to school aged children noted high coverage overall, with most children having received treatment on all three occasions (more than 7 doses of treatment were completed by 75% intervention group and 86% in the placebo group).¹⁴ However, a much lower proportion received all 9 doses of treatment (41% in the intervention group and 60% in the placebo group).¹⁴

In Mali, Clarke et al assessed a single round of sulfadoxine-pyrimethamine plus artesunate (SPAS) administered in school by teachers over three consecutive days.²² Coverage was high, with an overall average of 95% of students receiving the treatment (range across schools 90% to 100%), however, the fact that this was only a single round might have contributed to higher uptake.²²

School absenteeism was noted to be a barrier to reaching children through schools.¹² From an operational perspective, Staedke et al. noted that “school-based delivery is likely to be more feasible than community based delivery”, but that “further research is needed to explore feasibility and effects on larger scales.”¹² Additionally, when undertaking such a program, there is a need to consider how to address girls of reproductive age who should not be given certain antimalarials for prophylaxis without first confirming that they are not pregnant.¹²

In Mali, Thera et al. noted that close partnership with teachers is critical to maintain contact with students and ensure that any illnesses or adverse events are detected.³¹ A similar observation was made by Lalji et al. with respect to school bed net distribution.³²

In terms of utilizing schools as a distribution platform for malaria control interventions, a number of countries have explored the use of schools as a platform for distribution of ITNs; in the Southern Zone of Tanzania, the second round of a school-based net distribution program (SNP2) in 2014 successfully issued long lasting insecticide treated nets (LLINs) to 98% of eligible students and 96% of eligible teachers in the 3 targeted regions of Tanzania, based on review of registers.³² A pilot in Ghana similarly reported nearly 100% coverage among targeted individuals, however, a subsequent household survey found that only half of households with an eligible individual reported having received an LLIN through school-based distribution.²⁵ It is possible that the source was misclassified or not known by the respondent; this seems particularly plausible when considering that almost as many households owned school ITNs as owned ITNs from an unknown or discrepant source.²⁵ The data from the ITN programs suggest that a school-based platform can effectively reach its target audience, but highlight the potential issue in terms of achieving high community coverage.

Financial and economic considerations

There is relatively limited data on the cost of IPTsc. The economic cost of the IPTsc component of delivery of one therapeutic course of artesunate and sulfadoxine-pyrimethamine in Mali as part of a broader school-based prevention package cost \$2.72 per a child.³³ Human resources and the drug used were the leading drivers of cost. Intervention cost varied substantially based on treatment regimen selected. In this study, it was estimated that the cost of the intervention would be USD 1.27 less per child under seven years old if sulfadoxine-pyrimethamine (SP) and amodiaquine were used instead of artesunate and sulfadoxine-pyrimethamine.³³ Additionally, initial start-up costs of training and associated per diems of teachers would likely reduce should the intervention be repeated in the same schools with the same teachers.³³ Much of the published literature on IPTsc leverages schools and associated teachers for distribution, but IPTsc could be deployed at the community level targeting school-aged children. Community-based delivery of IPTsc would potentially require establishment of new community distributors, thereby increasing implementation cost.³⁴ A recently concluded randomized control trial of DP and ASAQ in Tanzania is expected to contribute additional data on IPTsc cost and cost-effectiveness when results are published.³⁵

One modeling study of cost-effectiveness of IPTsc in Kenya used data from a 2006 trial and estimated that the intervention cost \$1.88 per child treated per a year with treatment regimen and teacher training as the largest drivers of cost; it was assumed that no specific payment was made to teachers for delivering the intervention.³⁶ This included \$0.25 in setup cost and \$1.63 in recurrent costs per child.³⁶ The cost per a case of anemia averted was \$29.84 and the cost per *Plasmodium falciparum* parasitaemia averted was US\$ 5.36.³⁶ The largest drivers of cost-effectiveness were the effectiveness of the intervention and the background anemia prevalence.³⁶ Additionally, studies on school-based intermittent screening and treatment (IST) have some relevance for IPTsc. The cost of IST per child screened was \$6.24 per child in Kenya.³⁷

One study in Malawi, assessed the addition of antimalarial treatment to an already planned mass drug administration (MDA) for neglected tropical diseases (NTDs), and noted that this approach could improve the cost-benefit ratio of both interventions.¹⁸ A similar observation was made by Rehman et

al., who noted that Ugandan schoolchildren are already being engaged to deliver malaria intervention messages to their families and friends, thus adding in additional malaria control interventions into the same platform could leverage resources and potentially save costs.²³

Drug Resistance

Drug resistance is a critical issue to consider in any chemoprevention program. In Uganda, Nankabirwa et al. assessed the impact of repeated dosing of DP (either monthly or quarterly) to school children on the selection of drug resistance.³⁸ The study included 740 schoolchildren, and finger-prick blood samples were collected at enrollment, monthly, and with every episode of fever to assess for malaria infection by thick blood smear and for storage on filter paper. A total of 160 symptomatic and 1,522 asymptomatic episodes of *P. falciparum* parasitemia were documented. Of these, all 160 samples from symptomatic episodes, all 50 samples from children with recurrent parasitemia within 13 to 30 days of prior therapy with DP, and 600 samples randomly selected from children with either recurrent parasitemia >30 days after prior therapy with DP or from the control arm of the study were analyzed for drug resistance markers. In children who had received DP within the past 30 days, the prevalence of mutant genotypes *pfmdr1* N86Y and *pfprt* K76T, but not the other studied polymorphisms, were significantly than in children who had not been treated within 60 days (86Y, 18.0% versus 8.3% [P = 0.03]; 76T, 96.0% versus 86.1% [P = 0.05]), suggesting that DP use may select for parasites with decreased sensitivity to DP as well as ASAQ, but did not detect selection pressure for additional resistance mutations.

Modelling

Manore et al. utilized modeling to assess the effects of IPT on drug resistance and found that in general, resistance tends to be driven by drugs used for treatment in high transmission areas, and the role of IPT is minor. However, IPT can contribute to increased levels of resistance and loss of lives, particularly over longer time periods. They recommend that short half-life drugs such as AL be used for treatment, as this is less likely to drive resistance, and note that regular use of IPT with SP in children will result in potentially thousands of lives saved over the course of 5–10 years. However, the relative effect is dependent on resistance, such that “there are levels of resistance for which IPT saves lives over a short time period, but results in a cumulative loss of lives over 5–10 year periods as resistance levels ramp up. Therefore, our model suggests caution in using IPT without a corresponding heightened surveillance and awareness of changes in the circulating resistant strains over time. If resistance were to be significantly increasing over time, then evaluation of both the treatment drug and IPT usage would be warranted.”³⁹ Ross modeled DALYs averted and the cost per DALY averted by IPTi and IPTc; while the primary model focused on IPTc in children under 5, they also explored expanding the age range to older individuals, and found that in very low transmission settings, IPT would be more beneficial in older age groups with a peak at 20 years.⁴⁰

Disclaimer

The findings and conclusions in this paper are those of the authors and do not necessarily represent the views of the U.S. Centers for Disease Control and Prevention or the United States Agency for International Development (USAID).

Conclusion

There is some evidence on the acceptability, feasibility, equity, and relatively low cost of IPTsc. Schools provide a potentially attractive platform for delivery of health interventions and programs, and combining interventions in such platforms could reduce the cost per intervention and improve intervention package cost-effectiveness. In general, teachers and parents were appreciative of school-based efforts to target malaria, but it is important to ensure good community acceptance before embarking on a program to deliver drugs in schools. Based on results from school-based ITN distributions, a school platform appears relatively equitable, though there are considerations regarding who would be excluded from a school based program. Most of the programs conducted to date looked at relatively few rounds of distribution, thus the feasibility and compliance to more frequent or ongoing programs has yet to be evaluated. Nevertheless, the interventions had fairly low costs, the largest drivers of which were the treatments and human resources, both of which would vary by treatment regimen and frequency of distribution.

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Appendix.

Search Strategy, Update to Cohee et al.⁴¹

Search date: 12/23/21

Database	Strategy	Records
PubMed	asymptomatic[tiab] OR subpatent[tiab] OR carrier[tiab] OR symptomless[tiab] OR "carrier state"[mh] OR "asymptomatic infections"[mh] AND malaria[tiab] OR parasit*[tiab] OR plasmodi*[tiab] OR falciparum[tiab] OR malaria[mh] AND "seasonal malaria chemoprophylaxis"[tiab] OR "intermittent preventive treatment"[tiab] OR ipt[tiab] OR "intermittent preventive therapy"[tiab] OR iptc[tiab] OR iptsc[tiab] OR "intermittent preventive malaria treatment"[tiab] OR chemoprevention[tiab] OR chemosuppression[tiab] OR chemoprevention[mh] OR antimalarials[tiab] OR proguanil[tiab] OR atovaquone[tiab] OR malarone[tiab] OR doxycycline[tiab] OR mefloquine[tiab] OR larium[tiab] OR chloroquine[tiab] OR primaquine[tiab] OR aralen[tiab] OR quinine[tiab] OR qualaquin[tiab] OR hydroxychloroquine[tiab] OR plaquenil[tiab] OR "artemisinin-based combination therapy"[tiab] OR ACT[tiab] OR artesunate[tiab] OR Amodiaquine[tiab] OR Pyrimethamine[tiab] OR sulfadoxine[tiab] OR artemisinin[tiab] OR maloprim[tiab] OR dapson[tiab] OR chlorproguanil[tiab] OR Lapdap[tiab] OR Paludrine[tiab] OR Mepha[tiab] OR piperazine[tiab] OR Fansidar[tiab] OR antimalarials[mh] OR proguanil[mh] OR atovaquone[mh] OR "atovaquone, proguanil drug combination"[Supplementary Concept] OR doxycycline[mh] OR mefloquine[mh] OR chloroquine[mh] OR primaquine[mh] OR quinine[mh] OR hydroxychloroquine[mh] OR Artemisinins[mh] OR artesunate[Supplementary Concept] OR Amodiaquine[mh] OR Pyrimethamine[mh] OR sulfadoxine[mh] OR Maloprim[Supplementary Concept] OR dapson[tiab] OR chlorproguanil[Supplementary Concept] OR "chloroguanil,dapsone drug combination"[Supplementary Concept] OR clopidogrel[Supplementary Concept] OR piperazine[Supplementary Concept] OR "fanasil, pyrimethamine drug combination"[Supplementary Concept] AND child*[tiab] OR teenager[tiab] OR adolescen*[tiab] OR schoolage*[tiab] OR child[mh] OR adolescent[mh] AND ("2018/12/15" Date - Publication) : "present"[Date - Publication]	57

Embase (OVID) 1974-	(asymptomatic.ti,ab. OR subpatent.ti,ab. OR carrier.ti,ab. OR symptomless.ti,ab.) AND (malaria.ti,ab. OR parasit*.ti,ab. OR plasmodi*.ti,ab. OR falciparum.ti,ab.) AND (seasonal malaria chemoprophylaxis.ti,ab. OR intermittent preventive treatment.ti,ab. OR ipt.ti,ab. OR iptC.ti,ab. OR iptsc.ti,ab. OR intermittent preventive therapy.ti,ab. OR intermittent preventive malaria treatment.ti,ab. OR chemoprevention.ti,ab. OR chemosuppression.ti,ab. OR exp chemoprophylaxis/ OR antimalarials.ti,ab. OR proguanil.ti,ab. OR atovaquone.ti,ab. OR malarone.ti,ab. OR doxycycline.ti,ab. OR mefloquine.ti,ab. OR lariam.ti,ab. OR chloroquine.ti,ab. OR primaquine.ti,ab. OR aralen.ti,ab. OR quinine.ti,ab. OR qualaquin.ti,ab. OR hydroxychloroquine.ti,ab. OR plaquenil.ti,ab. OR artemisinin-based combination therapy.ti,ab. OR act.ti,ab. OR artesunate.ti,ab. OR amodiaquine.ti,ab. OR pyrimethamine.ti,ab. OR sulfadoxine.ti,ab. OR artemisinin.ti,ab. OR maloprim.ti,ab. OR dapsona.ti,ab. OR chlorproguanil.ti,ab. OR lapdap.ti,ab. OR paludrine.ti,ab. OR mepha.ti,ab. OR piperazine.ti,ab. OR fansidar.ti,ab. OR exp chemoprophylaxis/ OR exp antimalarial agent/ OR exp doxycycline/ OR exp sulfadoxine/ OR exp dapsona plus pyrimethamine/ OR exp dapsona/ OR exp chlorproguanil plus dapsona/) AND (child*.ti,ab. OR teenager.ti,ab. OR adolescen*.ti,ab. OR school age.ti,ab. OR school aged.ti,ab. OR exp child/ OR exp adolescent/) AND Dec 2018 -present	102-40 duplicates =62 unique items
Cochrane Central Register of Controlled Trials	(asymptomatic or subpatent or carrier or symptomless) AND (malaria or parasit* or plasmodi* or falciparum) AND (chemoprophylaxis or chemoprevention or chemosuppression or intermittent preventive or antimalarial*) AND (child* or teenage* or adolescen* or school-age*) LIMIT: PUBLICATION YEAR FROM Dec 2018 - 2021	40-14 duplicates =26 unique items
Clinicaltrials.gov	asymptomatic malaria OR subpatent malaria OR carrier malaria OR symptomless malaria First posted 12/15/2018 – 12/23/2021	5-0 duplicates =5 unique items

Notes: Duplicates were identified using the Endnote automated "find duplicates" function with preference set to match on title, author and year, and removed from your Endnote library. There will likely be additional duplicates found that Endnote was unable to detect.